

THE MEANING OF THE TERM PEDAGOGY AND ITS DEVELOPMENT AS A
SCIENCE AND EQUIVALENT MEANING OF PEDAGOGICAL TERMS IN ENGLISH
AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: the subject of education, the art of education. It is also a specific systematic activity aimed at forming a person, the science of the content, form and methods of education. Pedagogy is a collection of knowledge related to the field of upbringing and education. It was developed from the very ancient times and directly linked with different fields of various subjects. In this list it can be found the definitions for commonly used pedagogical terms. This list and the associated references and resources provide an overview of foundational concepts, teaching strategies, classroom structures, and philosophies. This page is meant as a quick reference and initial guide to these topics that may both answer a question and spark your curiosity to explore more deeply..

Keywords: terminological dictionaries, agrarian sector, Turkic languages, lexical units, affixes, lexical system, arabic agroterms, persian agroterms, irrigation, Pedagogical culture, Labor education, Aesthetic education, Economic education, Blended or Hybrid Course, Classroom Assessment Techniques (CATs)

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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ТЕРМИНА ПЕДАГОГИКА И ЕЕ РАЗВИТИЕ КАК НАУКИ И
ЭКВИВАЛЕНТНОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ В
АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Abstract: предмет воспитания, искусство воспитания. Это также конкретная систематическая деятельность, направленная на формирование личности, науки о содержании, форме и методах воспитания. Педагогика – это совокупность знаний, относящихся к области воспитания и образования. Она развивалась с древнейших времен и напрямую связана с разными областями различных предметов. В этом списке можно найти определения общеупотребительных педагогических терминов. Этот список и связанные с ним ссылки и ресурсы содержат обзор основополагающих концепций, стратегий обучения, структуры классных комнат и философии. Эта страница предназначена как краткий справочник и начальное руководство по этим темам, которые могут как ответить на вопрос, так и пробудить ваше любопытство к более глубокому изучению...

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INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILIDA PEDAGOGIKA TERMASINING MA'NOSI VA UNING
FAN SIFATIDA RIVOJLANISHI VA PEDAGOGIK TERMALARNING
EKVIVVALENT MA'NOSI.

Abstract: ta'lim predmeti, ta'lim san'ati. Shuningdek, u shaxsni shakllantirishga qaratilgan o'ziga xos tizimli faoliyat, ta'lim mazmuni, shakli va usullari haqidagi fandir. Pedagogika - bu tarbiya va ta'lim sohasiga oid bilimlar yig'indisidir. U juda qadim zamonlardan beri ishlab chiqilgan va turli fanlarning turli sohalari bilan bevosita bog'langan. Ushbu ro'yxatda keng tarqalgan pedagogik atamalarning ta'riflarini topish mumkin. Ushbu ro'yxat va tegishli havolalar va manbalar asosiy tushunchalar, o'qitish strategiyalari, sinf tuzilmalari va falsafalar haqida umumiy ma'lumot beradi. Ushbu sahifa savolga javob berishi va chuqurroq o'rganishga qiziqish uyg'otishi mumkin bo'lgan ushbu mavzular bo'yicha tezkor ma'lumotnoma va dastlabki qo'llanma sifatida mo'ljallangan.

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Pedagogy is the science of the general laws of education. **Pedagogy** - Greek, **pais** - child, **agogos** - leading - child means leader. Your humanity is enlightened and spiritual pedagogue as a result of changes in his attitude towards excellence. The science of **pedagogy** (the art of introducing a child to the right life) is unique among the people got a prestigious position. In this way, science that educates people; as **pedagogy** has taken a special place among the system of secular sciences.

The term pedagogy is interpreted as follows in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. **Pedagogue** (Greek-educator) pedagogic specialist; a teacher, a person who is engaged in education and training of children and generations, who has special training in this field.

It is also interpreted as follows in the Webster Dictionary of English Usage: **Pedagogue** 1. Bryson 1984 says that pedagogue means the same thing as pedant. Our evidence shows that it does not. Bryson's statement is a bit like saying politician means "crook." The categories may overlap in some cases, but the words do not have the same meaning. Pedagogue means "teacher" – whether a boring teacher or a fascinating one: McCracken was the essence of the pedagogue, his presentations to the President having the bloodless quality of professional lectures in Economics 100 - Rowland Evans, Jr. & Robert D. Novak, Atlantic, July 1971

The ballet faculty, which included that most distinguished pedagogue from Paris, Madame Nova - Walter Terry, Saturday Rev., 16 Oct. 1976

The spelling *pedagog*, which seems to have been born in the spelling reform movement of the late 19th century, is still sometimes used: . . . abdication of parent, priest, and pedagog – F. R. Buckley, N.Y. Times, 20 Nov. 1972

Education and training is the formation of a person as a person its incomparable importance has been known since ancient times. It is known that, this is ancient Greece and Rome that was formed in ancient Antiquity which effects to the ancient Eastern and Western civilizations development, scientific, cultural, educational formation of the community and civilizations that had an incomparable influence on its development. Education and society in ancient Greece and Rome considered an integral part of his life and separate in social life took place. A free

person is a person who is not subject to slavery considered it his duty to get an education.

The educational systems in these regions aimed to develop the social interaction, preservation of customs, cultural and historical traditions and customs. In each administrative region (The territory of ancient Greece was administratively called **polis** divided into regions) schools are distinguished by their own characteristics organization of accommodation and educational process with each other was seriously different in terms of content. But in general, organization of the educational process and forms of education during this period was almost the same.

In ancient Greece, two polis were considered of particular important- **Sparta** in Laconia (*Qadyun. Lakedemori*) and Afina in Attica. These two city-states are known from history. Along with being considered the cradle and founder of Western civilization the unique educational culture formed in them later on determined the directions of formation of education in the West.

The main goal of the Spartan education and training system was to train the warrior-citizen, and the main focus was on the physical fitness and development of the ulama. Special attention is also paid to spiritual preparation training, with a great emphasis on the formation of determination, initiative and loyalty.

Spartan education and training system **agoge** ("to pluck") was a "Spartan education" method which was training a warrior-citizen boy from 7 to 30 years old. Only free citizens (Spartiates and perieks), that is, people who were not subject to slavery, their children forced recruits and people from other strata and categories, for example, the children of immigrants and slaves were involved in the education process is considered the highest honor.

Boys from 7 to 15 years of age are military type were trained in special boarding schools (*ill and aggella*). The practice of military games in training, they were also engaged in music, singing and dancing. Also taught to write, read and clearly, fluently and culture of speech in Lakonia ("laconic" speech - the region of Laconia derived from the name) skills were also formed. The control of Ill and aggellalami were done by *paydonoms* (educators).

Antiquity, which left a rich spiritual heritage to the whole world era (**lat. antiquitas- ancient era**: VII-II centuries BC, in which the ancient Greco-Roman civilization is understood) many determined the development of civilization and in them gave impetus to the formation of science and culture. In Athens, training and education is known as **paydeyya** (**paydeyya**- Old Greek. child rearing; peyados - child, teenager) and that as a category of philosophy by contemporary thinkers considered and in the current language "taiim system", a certain form of education can be understood as a model.

It is a rich aspect of Athenian education and the Antiquity in general it was that people became famous poets and writers to know his works by heart and to the level of art in front of the public it was a tradition to read aloud. Students are the same famous poets, writers, historians and philosophers, poems, poems, tragedies and "historical comedies", gnomes (short didactic texts), myths and legends, hymns and other types of literary works were memorized.

As the main didactic method of teaching for winter students read each piece of text read by the teacher they repeated out loud together. Teaching arithmetic was interesting because the teachers were using authentic items were used as an exhibition. In the period of teaching counting, **the counting board (abac)** is the main and most important considered an effective didactic tool. After getting the sufficient knowledge on the subject of social science, general physical and basic military training in gymnasium schools (palestrums). Gymnastic exercises and military in the gymnasium preparation was carried out under the control of the state and this process led by specially appointed pedotribes.

Pedagogik madaniyat - Pedagogical culture is a characteristic of a teacher's personality, his behavior in the conditions of educational and educational activities. it is considered as an important part of the teacher's general culture, which is manifested in the system of professional qualities and the specific characteristics of pedagogical activity. In some cases, they also speak of a psychological and pedagogical culture - a specific professional category, which is used to indicate the degree to which the teacher has mastered pedagogical experience.

Mehnat ta'limi - Labor education -joint activities of teachers and students aimed at developing general work skills and abilities, psychol. readiness for work, formation of a responsible attitude to work and its products, conscious choice of profession. Method V - to include the student in the full composition of work: planning, organization, implementation, control, evaluation.

Estetik tarbiya - Aesthetic education - purposeful interaction of educators and students, to develop and improve the ability to perceive, correctly understand, appreciate and create beauty in life and art in a growing person, to the laws of beauty in creativity helps to create a suitable.

Iqtisodiy ta'lim - Economic education is a teacher and teacher aimed at forming knowledge, skills and abilities, needs, interest and way of thinking in accordance with the nature, principles and norms of rational management and organization of production, distribution and consumption. 'targeted student interaction.

Ijtimoiy ta'lim - Social education - the process and result of a person's spontaneous interaction with his immediate living environment and target educational conditions (family, spiritual, moral, civil, legal, religious, etc.); the

process of active adaptation of a person to certain roles, normative relations and social forms, creation of conditions for the purposeful development of a person in the process of socialization.

Kompyuter savodxonligi -Computer literacy is part of technology education. Geological complex includes: knowledge of the basic concepts of informatics and computer technology; knowledge of the basic structure and functionality of computer technologies; knowledge of modern operating systems and mastering their basic commands; knowledge of modern software shells and general-purpose operating tools (Norton Commander, Windows, their extensions) and their functions; have at least one text editor; basic understanding of algorithms, languages and programming packages; initial experience using utilities.

Didaktika - Didactic (from Greek didaktikos - meaning to receive, teach) - theory of education and upbringing, a branch of pedagogy. The subject of teaching is teaching as a means of educating and educating a person, that is, in the unity of education and training, which ensures that the educational content organized by the teacher is mastered by students. D functions: theoretical (diagnostic and prognostic) and practical (normative, instrumental). **Didaktik qoidalar -Didactic rules** - instructions reveal individual aspects of the application of a certain educational principle. For example, one of the rules for implementing the vision principle is: use different views, but do not allow them to become too numerous.

Haqiqiy baholash - Authentic Assessment: Assessments in which student learners demonstrate learning by applying their knowledge to authentic, complex, real-world tasks or simulations. Proponents of authentic assessment argue that these types of knowledge checks “help students rehearse for the complex ambiguities of the ‘game’ of adult and professional life” (Wiggins, 1990, p.1).

Aralashtirilgan yoki gibrid kurs - Blended or Hybrid Course: Blended or hybrid courses are “classes in which some percentage of seat time has been reduced and replaced with online content and activities” (Darby & Lang 2019, p.). These courses continue to meet in-person for some percentage of the class time but content, activities, assessments, and other ways for students to engage with content are delivered online. It is important to note that these courses are intentionally designed to utilize both in-person and online class time to achieve effective student learning.

Sinfni baholash usullari (CATs) - Classroom Assessment Techniques (CATs): “An approach designed to help teachers find out what students are learning in the classroom and how well they are learning it. This approach is learner-centered, teacher-directed, mutually beneficial, formative, context-specific, ongoing, and firmly rooted in good practice”. Through using a CAT the instructor is able to gather formative feedback on students learning to inform future teaching.

In conclusion, it can be said that Sparta is a system of education and upbringing coach, educator, teacher, adults, political and state figures unconditional obedience and personal worldview of the students should not be fully configured. Such is education and upbringing principles can be observed in the ancient Eastern educational culture. Conservatism to such educational systems, strictness to coaches obedience, only on the basis of the example shown by the teacher to have knowledge and skills, clear actions repetition is typical. The terms related to pedagogy coexist in both language and the meaning and functions of each term are similar. If people who are not aware of the science of pedagogy, pedagogy when they learn science on time and use their achievements effectively young people even more they were better educated. People who are well aware of pedagogy, their knowledge stay in the experience that they didn't get it for also in the process of education those who did not succeed.

REFERENCE:

O'zbek tilining Izohli lug'ati, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar Akademiyasi Alisher Navoiy Noidagi Til Va Adabiyot Institute.

Darby & Lang 2019, (2017) Teaching Online A Practical Guide, Routledge

PEDAGOGIKA, J. Hasanboyev, X.A. T o'raqulov, I.Sh. Alqarov, N .O 'Usmanov; «NOSHIR» TOSHKENT 2016

Webster' s Dictionary of English Usage, Philippines Copyright 1989 by Merriam-WebsterInc..

Wiggins, G. (1998). Ensuring authentic performance. Educative assessment: Designing assessments to inform and improve student performance. Jossey-Bass, p. 21-42.

<https://ctl.wustl.edu/resources/glossary-of-pedagogical-terms/>

<https://apriori-nauka.ru/uz/graphics/slovar-osnovnyh-pedagogicheskikh-terminov-slovar-sovremennyh.html>